

Enhancing Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia Diagnosis Using HSV Colour Space Segmentation

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Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) is a rapidly progressing form blood cancer that affects children. Early and accurate diagnosis is important for effective treatment, but manually examining blood smear images under a microscope is time consuming, depends on the expertise of pathologists, and can happen classification mistakes due to human error. To overcome above mentioned challenges, this study introduces an automated detection system, that combines image processing with deep learning. Specifically, it shows how the HSV (Hue, Saturation, and Value) color space can use for image segmentation and uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for classification and automatic detection of ALL cells. The methodology begins by preprocessing peripheral blood smear images taken from a microscopic camera, converting them from the standard RGB to the HSV color space model. A track bar-based thresholding technique is applied to extract the nucleus from ALL cells and other cells from the background, ensuring effective extraction. Additionally, morphological operations refine the extracted features, improving the accuracy of cell identification. These processed images are used to train a CNN model, which classifies cells in the microscopic image as ALL cells and non-ALL cells based on key features like shape, texture, and color intensity of the nucleus. To extract the purple color nucleus, the lower HSV values were adjusted to Hue=54, Saturation=0, and Value=135, while the upper HSV values were set to Hue=178, Saturation=113, and Value=255 after fine-tuning. A mask was used to remove the background and separate the nucleus. The upper HSV range corresponds to light purple color, while the lower HSV range corresponds to dark purple color. The system was trained using a CNN and then tested with a dataset of blood smear images taken with a microscope. It takes approximately 30 seconds to identify the cells, achieving a classification accuracy of 98.53%. Compared to manual diagnosis, this HSV color space-based automated approach significantly reduces diagnostic time and minimizes the chances of human error. The results demonstrate the potential of combining image processing and deep learning for the detection of ALL, making the system a valuable tool for hematology laboratories and hospitals.

Keywords: HSV color space, leukemia, CNN, image processing, ALL